

Mass Spectral Fragmentation Patterns of Some 4-[5-Aryl-2-furfurylidene]-3-mercapto-5-substituted-1,2,4-triazoles and 6-(5-Aryl-2-furyl)-1,2,4-triazolo[3,4-*b*]-1,3,4-thiadiazoles[†]

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Several 4-(5-aryl-2-furfurylidene)amino-3-mercapto-5-substituted-1,2,4-triazoles (**1**) have been synthesized and converted into 6-(5-aryl-2-furyl)-1,2,4-triazolo[3,4-*b*]-1,3,4-thiadiazoles (**2**).

Triazoles and their fused derivatives¹ and 1,3,4-thiadiazoles² are associated with various biological activities. Keeping these observations in view, 6-(5-aryl-2-furyl)-1,2,4-triazolo[3,4-*b*]-1,3,4-thiadiazoles (**3**) were synthesized starting from 4-(5-aryl-2-furfurylidene)amino-3-mercapto-1,2,4-triazoles (**1**) by employing a 30% solution of bromine in glacial acetic acid. As a part of structural investigation, mass spectra of five Schiff bases (**1a-e**) and six cyclized products (**3a-f**) were recorded. The mass spectral decomposition modes of various triazolothiadiazoles and Schiff bases containing arylfuran substituents have been investigated.

Results and Discussion

All the spectra showed characteristic common fragmentation pathways. In most cases, intense molecular ion peaks were observed confirming aromatic nature of the cyclized products. Molecular ions of the Schiff bases **1a-c** were observed at *m/z* 329, 343 and 332/334 corresponding to the molecular formulae C₁₄H₁₁N₅O₃S and C₁₅H₁₃N₅O₃S and C₁₅H₁₃ClN₄OS respectively. The molecular ions of **1a** and **1b** underwent fragmentation to produce molecular ions at *m/z* 214 corresponding to the molecular ion of *p*-nitrophenylfuronitrile. A peak at *m/z* 203 found in the spectrum of **1c** as a base peak corresponded to the molecular ion of *o*-chlorophenylfuronitrile. The ion at *m/z* 214 further underwent loss of NO, NO and CO to give peaks at *m/z* 184 and *m/z* 156 respectively, being a characteristic fragmentation pattern of nitrophenylfuran derivatives³. The molecular ions of Schiff bases **1a-c** were also found to undergo fragmentations to produce molecular ions of triazoles at *m/z* 115, 129 and 211/213 respectively (Scheme 1).

Arylfuronitriles **2a** and **2c** were found to undergo characteristic fragmentation pattern. The loss of carbon mo-

Scheme 1. Mass spectral fragmentation pattern of Schiff bases.

noxide and CN radical from the molecular ions, **2a** (14.1%) and **2c** (100%) resulted in the formation of arylpropenyl cations (species *a*) at *m/z* 160 (28.0%) and 149/151 (50.7%) respectively. The loss of Cl from **2c** and NO₂ from **2a** gave a common ion peak at *m/z* 168 (species *b*; 3.5% and 18.0% respectively). Subsequent loss of CO from this ion (*m/z* 168) resulted in another common ion peak at *m/z* 140 (46.1% and 33.7%).

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The mass spectra of triazolothiadiazoles **3a**, **3b**, **3c** and **3e** showed intense molecular ion peaks at m/z 327, 341, 355 and 316/318, consistent with the molecular formulae

% Abundance of molecular ion peaks :

Compound	R	R ¹	m/z	Abundance (%)
3a	<i>o</i> -Cl	CH ₃	316/318	9.8
3b	<i>p</i> -Cl	CH ₃	316/318	20.0
3c	<i>o</i> -NO ₂	CH ₃	327	46.2
3d	<i>o</i> -NO ₂	Et	341	29.3
3e	<i>p</i> -NO ₂	Et	341	5.0
3f	<i>o</i> -NO ₂	Pr	355	43.9

m/z Values (% abundance) of fragment ions (**3i**) in compounds **3a-f** :

R	m/z	Abundance (%)
<i>o</i> -Cl	221/223	2.7 in 3a
<i>p</i> -Cl	221/223	10 in b
<i>o</i> -NO ₂	232	1.1 in c
<i>o</i> -NO ₂	232	(-) in d
<i>p</i> -NO ₂	232	5 in e
<i>o</i> -NO ₂	232	(-) in f

m/z Values (% abundance) of fragment ions (**3j**) in compounds **3a-f**

R	m/z	Abundance (%)
<i>o</i> -Cl	177/179	(-) in 3aa
<i>p</i> -Cl	177/179	(-) in b
<i>o</i> -NO ₂	188	7.4 in c
<i>o</i> -NO ₂	188	6.5 in d
<i>p</i> -NO ₂	188	1.0 in e
<i>o</i> -NO ₂	188	2.5 in f

m/z Values (% abundance) of fragment ions (**3k**) in compounds **3a-f**

R	m/z	Abundance (%)
<i>o</i> -Cl	149/151	84.9 in 3a
<i>p</i> -Cl	149/151	10.0 in b
<i>o</i> -NO ₂	160	8.1 in c
<i>o</i> -NO ₂	160	6.5 in d
<i>p</i> -NO ₂	160	10.0 in e
<i>o</i> -NO ₂	160	4.4 in f

Chart 1

$C_{14}H_9N_5O_3S$, $C_{15}H_{11}N_5O_3S$, $C_{16}H_{13}N_5O_3S$ and $C_{14}H_9ClN_4OS$ respectively. These molecular ions underwent fragmentations to give species **3i** at m/z 232 and 221/223 (Chart 1) which on expulsion of CS generated ion species (**3j**) at m/z 188 and 177/179. The latter on further loss of CO gave finally the species **3k** at m/z 160 and 149/151 respectively. The peaks corresponding to arylfuronitrile were not observed in these cases.

Experimental

3-Substituted-4-amino-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazoles were prepared according to literature methods⁴. Arylfurfurals were obtained through Meerwein reaction⁵.

6-(5-Aryl-2-furyl)-3-methyl-1,2,4-triazolo[3,4-b]-1,3,4-thiadiazoles (**3**): The Schiff base (**1**; 10 mmol) was suspended in glacial acetic acid (10 ml) and a solution of bromine in glacial acetic acid (5 ml; 30%) was added with stirring for about 30 min, and the solution was set aside for 16 h. The resulting solid was washed with water, dried and crystallized from dimethylformamide-ethanol (2 : 1).

Mass spectra were recorded on a Jeol D-300 spectrometer (70 eV).

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